

Statistical fractal inference

Roberto N. Padua¹Dexter S. Ontoy²Daisy R. Palompon²Joy M. Mirasol³**NORSU - BSU, Philippines¹****Cebu Normal University, Philippines²****Bukidnon State University, Philippines³**

dexter_s_ontoy@yahoo.com

Date Submitted: September 7, 2015

Date Accepted: September 22, 2015

ABSTRACT

The inverse power law distributions are used as the model for fractal probability distributions that have fractional exponents (λ) and such that the transformation $X(1-\lambda)$ is uniformly distributed. The paper examines aspects of point estimation and tests of hypotheses about statistical fractals. It is shown that the maximum likelihood estimator of the fractional dimension λ is uniformly minimum variance unbiased estimator (UMVUE) using the Lehmann-Scheffe's theorem and also that the likelihood ratio test for $H_0: \lambda = \lambda_0$ is uniformly most powerful (UMPT) by the Neymann-Pearson Lemma. The paper likewise explains that the test for equality of two medians of two fractal distributions is equivalent to a test for the equality of the fractal dimensions. In fact, the result is generalized to the test for the equality of two α th quantiles of two fractal distributions. The test for the equality of two fractal distributions is compared with the Mann-Whitney U test and with the Student's t-test for independent samples in terms of robustness and asymptotic Pitman efficiency.

Keywords: *fractal dimension, maximum likelihood, quantiles, test of hypothesis*

I. INTRODUCTION

In an earlier paper, Padua, Barabat, Borres & Salazar et al. (2013) considered statistical descriptive measures for fractal observations. The authors suggested the use of the α^{th} quantile, x_{α} , as a replacement of the (non-existent) mean of fractal observations, and the ruggedness index, I_R , for the corresponding (non-existent) notion of variance. Evidence of the inappropriateness of normal distribution theory in dealing with the inherent ruggedness and irregularities of real-world data are mounting (e.g. Mandelbrot, 1967; Devaney, 1988, Selvam, 2008) so that a corresponding fractal statistical analysis theory needs to be developed. We pursue this objective in this paper by establishing the framework for

statistical inference of fractal observations.

Classical statistical inference makes use of the sample mean \bar{x} as an estimate of the true mean (μ), whenever the latter exists, for mathematical simplicity (Selvam, 2008). The sample mean, \bar{x} , is an unbiased estimator of μ whose variance decreases with increasing sample size (n). Moreover, for large n , \bar{x}_n behaves like a normal random variable with mean, μ , and variance, $\frac{\sigma^2}{n}$. Indeed, this mathematical tractability of \bar{x}_n is enshrined in the famous Central Limit Theorem as postulated by De Moivre which is often cited as a justification for using the simple average in most statistical analysis. When the mean (μ) does not exist, however, the entire classical statistical

inference based on normal distribution collapses.

However, most situations or phenomena in the real world involve a mean that does not exist such as earthquakes, stock market crashes, student test scores, and the like (Selvam, 2008). It is for this specific reason that statistical fractals are developed. This branch of statistics is in its infant stage despite a long history of recognition that most data/observations do not subscribe to a normal probability distribution. Indeed, mathematical statisticians attempted to fit an otherwise highly rugged, self-similar and irregular set of observations to a comfortable and safe normal theory. For instance, in the 1990's, large or unusually small observations

were treated as "outliers" or deviants which can be treated by Robust Statistics. The notion that these outliers were not deviants but really part of a usual phenomenon came much later. In fact, in an attempt to put Robust Statistics as part of classical statistics, some proponents suggested "throwing away" the outliers (see Huber [1981] for an excellent account of Robust Statistics).

Stochastic self-similarity at various scales is a notion that most probably account for most of natural processes. Such a view provides new lenses from which to study cold data in order to extract information lost by the smoothing process of classical statistical inference.

II. Fractal Statistical Inference

Let \mathcal{J} be the class of power law distributions parameterized by θ , $\theta \geq x$ for all x , and λ , the fractal dimension:

[1] ... $\mathcal{J} = \left\{ f_{\lambda}: [\theta, \infty] \rightarrow R^+ \mid f_{\lambda}(x) = \frac{\lambda-1}{\theta} \left(\frac{x}{\theta}\right)^{-\lambda} \right\}$. Let $\Omega = \{(\theta, \lambda) \subseteq R_+^2\}$ be the parametric domain, $\Omega \subseteq R^2$. Let x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n be a random sample from $f_{\lambda}(x; \theta) \in F$. On the basis of the information contained in x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n , we wish to develop tests of hypotheses about λ and θ .

II.1 Point Estimation

The likelihood function $L(x; \theta)$ can be derived as:

$$[2] \dots L = \prod_{i=1}^n f_{\lambda}(x_i; \theta) = \left[\frac{\lambda-1}{\theta} \right]^n \prod_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{x_i}{\theta} \right)^{-\lambda}.$$

The corresponding log - likelihood function is:

$$[3] \dots \text{Log } L = n \log \frac{\lambda-1}{\theta} - \lambda \sum_{i=1}^n \log \left(\frac{x_i}{\theta} \right).$$

The maximum likelihood estimators (MLE) of λ and θ respectively are:

$$[4] \dots \hat{\lambda} = 1 + n \left[\sum_{i=1}^n \log \left(\frac{x_i}{\theta} \right) \right]^{-1}$$

$$\hat{\theta} = \min\{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\},$$

Properties of the Estimators $\hat{\lambda}$ and $\hat{\theta}$

We show that the MLE for λ is unbiased for λ .

Proof: Take $n = 1$ and $\hat{\lambda} = 1 + \left[\log \left(\frac{x}{\theta} \right) \right]^{-1}$ and so:

$$\begin{aligned} E(\hat{\lambda}) &= 1 + E\left(\frac{1}{\log\left(\frac{x}{\theta}\right)}\right) \\ &= 1 + \frac{(\lambda-1)}{\theta} \int_{\theta}^{\infty} \frac{\left(\frac{x}{\theta}\right)^{-\lambda}}{\log\left(\frac{x}{\theta}\right)} dx \end{aligned}$$

Let $u = \log\left(\frac{x}{\theta}\right)$, $x = \theta e^u$ and $dx = \theta e^u du$

$$E(\hat{\lambda}) = 1 + (\lambda - 1) \int_0^{\infty} \frac{e^{-(\lambda-1)u}}{u} du$$

Now:

$$\int_0^{\infty} \frac{e^{-(\lambda-1)u}}{u} du = \int_0^{\infty} u^{-1} e^{-(\lambda-1)u} du.$$

We recognize the last integral as a Gamma function with $\alpha = 0$, $\beta = \frac{1}{\lambda-1}$. Thus:

$$\int_0^{\infty} \frac{e^{-(\lambda-1)u}}{u} du = \int_0^{\infty} u^{-1} e^{-(\lambda-1)u} du = \frac{\left(\frac{1}{\lambda-1}\right)^0 \Gamma(0)}{1} = 1.$$

Alternatively, we can use Complex Integration to show this last statement.

Hence:

$$E(\hat{\lambda}) = 1 + (\lambda - 1) = \lambda.$$

Now, for a sample of size n , $E(\hat{\lambda}) = 1 + n \left[E \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \log \left(\frac{x}{\theta} \right)^{-1} \right) \right]$
becomes: $E(\hat{\lambda}) = 1 + n \cdot \frac{(\lambda-1)}{n} = \lambda$.

Since $\hat{\lambda}$ is the MLE of λ , it possesses other desirable properties, namely that it is consistent and also asymptotically normal with mean λ and variance equal to $\frac{1}{I(\lambda)}$ where $I(\lambda)$ is the Fisher's information number. Likewise, since it is a function

of sufficient statistics, we are only required to show completeness of the distribution of X to be able to use Lehmann Scheffe's Theorem to prove that it is UMVUE.

Theorem 1: The random variable X from a fractal distribution comes from a family of complete distributions.

Proof:

Let $g(x)$ be any function of x such that $E(g(x)) = 0$. Then: $E(g(x)) = \frac{\lambda-1}{\theta} \int_{\theta}^{\infty} g(x) \left(\frac{x}{\theta}\right)^{-\lambda} dx = 0$. This reduces to: $\int_{\theta}^{\infty} \frac{g(x)}{x^{\lambda}} dx = 0$. For the improper integral to exist, $g(x) \alpha O\left(\frac{1}{x^{\delta}}\right)$ where $\delta > 1 - \lambda$ and so: $\int_{\theta}^{\infty} \frac{k}{x^{\lambda+\delta}} dx = 0$. Hence: $\frac{k}{1-\lambda-\delta} \cdot \frac{k}{x^{\lambda+\delta-1}} \Big|_{\theta}^{\infty} = 0$.

The last equation implies that:

$$\frac{1}{\theta^{\lambda+\delta-1}} = 0$$

Further implying that $\delta \rightarrow \infty$ since θ is finite. It follows that $g(x) = \frac{A}{x^{\delta}} \rightarrow 0$ and thus: $g(x) \equiv 0$ a.e. so X comes from a complete family of distributions.

By the Lehmann-Scheffe's theorem, we conclude that $\hat{\lambda}$ must be a uniformly minimum variance unbiased estimator of λ (U.M. V. U. E.):

Theorem 2: Let $\hat{\lambda}$ be the MLE of λ . Then, $\hat{\lambda}$ is function of complete sufficient statistics; $\hat{\lambda}$ is unbiased for λ and so λ is the uniformly minimum variance unbiased estimator (UMVUE) of λ .

Proof:

Since $\hat{\lambda}$ is the MLE of λ , it is always a function of sufficient statistics. Theorem 1 shows that it is complete while we have shown that $E(\hat{\lambda}) = \lambda$. It follows from the Lehmann Scheffe's theorem that $\hat{\lambda}$ is UMVUE of λ .

The likelihood ratio test (LRT) statistic:

$$(5) \dots \Psi = \frac{\sup L(x; \lambda)}{L(x; \lambda_0)}$$

rejects H_0 if $\Psi > 1$ or equivalently, where $\log \Psi > 0$. However, $\sup L(x; \lambda) = L(x; \hat{\lambda})$ where maximizes $L(x; \lambda)$ and $\hat{\lambda}$ is the MLE. It follows that the likelihood ratio test (LRT) becomes:

$$(6) \quad L = \frac{\left(\frac{\hat{\lambda}-1}{\theta}\right)^n \cdot \left(\frac{x_1}{\theta}\right)^{-\hat{\lambda}} \dots \left(\frac{x_n}{\theta}\right)^{-\hat{\lambda}}}{\left(\frac{\lambda_0-1}{\theta}\right)^n \left(\frac{x_1}{\theta}\right)^{-\lambda_0} \dots \left(\frac{x_n}{\theta}\right)^{-\lambda_0}} > 1$$

$$L = \frac{(\hat{\lambda}-1)}{(\lambda_0-1)} \cdot \left(\frac{x_1}{\theta}\right)^{\lambda_0-\hat{\lambda}} \dots \left(\frac{x_n}{\theta}\right)^{\lambda_0-\hat{\lambda}}$$

Before performing any of the statistical test of hypotheses suggested in this paper on a set of observations, it is expedient to ascertain that the observations indeed come from a fractal probability distribution. To do this, we use Theorem 2 of the paper of Padua et al. (2013) which required: (a.) that the maximum likelihood estimator of the fractal dimension be fractional (non-integral), and (b.) that the distribution of $X(1-\lambda)$ be uniform. We recommend the analytical representation of a Q-Q plot to test the latter (see Ryan-Joiner test).

The simplest situation in statistical inference is when we are interested in testing: $H_0: \lambda = \lambda_0$ versus $H_a: \lambda \neq \lambda_0$. For instance, we may be interested in determining whether or not x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n are non-fractal observations viz: $H_0: \lambda = 0$; $H_0: \lambda = 1$; etc. If they are not, then we can use classical statistical inference in pursuing the study.

or equivalently:

$$(7) \quad \log L = \log \frac{(\hat{\lambda}-1)}{(\lambda_0-1)} + (\lambda_0 - \hat{\lambda}) \sum_{i=1}^n \log \left(\frac{x_i}{\theta} \right) > 0$$

Let $Z = \frac{\hat{\lambda}-\lambda_0}{\hat{\lambda}-1}$, then the left - hand side of (7) becomes:

$$(8)... \quad Z = \frac{(\hat{\lambda}-\lambda_0) \sum_{i=1}^n \log \left(\frac{x_i}{\theta} \right)}{\log(\hat{\lambda}-1) - \log(\lambda_0-1)} < Z_\alpha$$

with a decision criterion that says, "reject H_0 iff $z < z_\alpha$, z_α is the $(1 - \alpha)^{th}$ quantile of the distribution of z under H_0 ." We note that Z is close to zero when H_0 is true.

In order to derive the null distribution of z , we can use a simpler form of (8) :

$$(9)... \quad Z = (\hat{\lambda} - \lambda_0) \sum_{i=1}^n \log \left(\frac{x_i}{\theta} \right)$$

We find the distribution of $y = (\hat{\lambda} - \lambda_0) \log \left(\frac{x_i}{\theta} \right)$ first:

Theorem 3: The null distribution of the random variable

$$y = (\hat{\lambda} - \lambda_0) \log \left(\frac{x_i}{\theta} \right) \text{ if } f_\lambda(x) = \frac{(\lambda_0-1)}{\theta} \left(\frac{x}{\theta} \right)^{-\lambda_0} \text{ is:}$$

$$g(y) = \frac{(\lambda-1)}{(1-\lambda_0)} e^{-\frac{(\lambda-1)}{(1-\lambda_0)}(y-1)}, \quad 1 < y < \infty,$$

an exponential distribution.

Proof:

From:

$$y = (\hat{\lambda} - \lambda_0) \sum \log \left(\frac{x_i}{\theta} \right)$$

Rewrite to:

$$y = (1 - \lambda_0) \sum \log \left(\frac{x_i}{\theta} \right) + n$$

$$y - n = r \sum \log \left(\frac{x_i}{\theta} \right) \text{ where } r = (1 - \lambda_0)$$

Let $n=1$:

$$y - 1 = r \log \left(\frac{x_i}{\theta} \right)$$

$$\log \left(\frac{x_i}{\theta} \right) = \frac{y-1}{r}$$

$$x = \theta e^{\frac{y-1}{r}}$$

So that the Jacobian of the transformation is: $\frac{dx}{dy} = \frac{\theta}{r} e^{\frac{y-1}{r}}$

It follows that:

$$g(y) = \left(\frac{y-1}{\theta}\right) \left(\frac{\theta e^{\frac{y-1}{r}}}{\theta}\right)^{-\lambda} \cdot \frac{\theta}{r} e^{\frac{y-1}{r}}$$

$$g(y) = \frac{(\lambda-1)}{r} e^{-\frac{(\lambda-1)}{r}(y-1)}$$

$$g(y) = \frac{(\lambda-1)}{(1-\lambda_0)} e^{-\frac{(\lambda-1)}{(1-\lambda_0)}(y-1)}$$

The moment - generating function of y is:

$$(10) \dots m_y(t) = \frac{1}{1-rt},$$

and so the moment - generating function of $z = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n Y_i$ where y_1, \dots, y_n are iid from (10) is:

$$(11) \dots m_z(t) = \left(\frac{1}{1-rt/n}\right)^n$$

which is the moment-generating function of a Gamma random variable with $\alpha = n$ and $\beta = \frac{r}{n}$.

It follows that the null distribution of z is:

$$(12) \quad h(z) = \frac{1}{\frac{r-n}{n} \Gamma(n)} z^{n-1} e^{-\frac{n}{r}z} \quad , z \geq 0.$$

The $(1 - \alpha)^{th}$ quantile of z can be obtained from (12).

Relationship Between - Fractal Dimension (λ) and the Median ($\tilde{\mu}$).

In this section, we show that if $\lambda_1 > \lambda_2$ then $\tilde{\mu}_1 > \tilde{\mu}_2$, that is observations with higher fractal dimension also have higher medians.

Let $x \sim f_\lambda(x)$, then:

$$F_\lambda(\tilde{\mu}) = \frac{1}{2} \quad \text{or} \quad 1 - \left(\frac{\tilde{\mu}}{\theta}\right)^{1-\lambda} = \frac{1}{2}$$

$$(13) \dots \tilde{\mu} = 2^{\lambda-1} \theta$$

It follows from (13) that if $\lambda_1 > \lambda_2$, then $2^{\lambda_1-1} > 2^{\lambda_2-1}$ so $\tilde{\mu}_1 > \tilde{\mu}_2$ is equivalent to a test for the equality of the median of two fractal distributions.

Theorem 4: The likelihood ratio test (LRT) for the equality of two fractal dimensions is equivalent to a test for the equality of the median of two fractal distributions.

Alternative Non-Parametric Test

When the interest is on comparing two (2) probability distributions (rather than their roughness), we can use a non-parametric method called Mann-Whitney U test. The Mann-Whitney U test is a non-parametric method for testing hypothesis that one of two samples of independent observations tends to have larger values than the other.

Important assumptions necessary for a very general formulation of the Mann-Whitney U test is discussed at length in the papers of Nachar (2008), McKnight & Najab (2010), and Fay & Proschan (2010).

From these assumptions, a convenient formula for this test can be derived as follows:

The ranks will be added for the observations from the sample 1. The sum of ranks in sample 2 will then be determinate, because the sum of all the ranks is equal to $N(N + 1)/2$ where N is the total number of observations.

U is now given by:

where n_1 is the sample size for sample 1, and R_1 is the sum of the ranks in sample 1.

Note that it does not matter which of the two samples is considered sample 1. An equally valid formula for U is

The smaller value of U_1 and U_2 is the one used when consulting significance tables. The sum of the two values is given by knowing that $R_1 + R_2 = N(N + 1)/2$ and $N = n_1 + n_2$, and doing some algebra, we find that the sum is comparable to Student's t -test and to the Likelihood Ratio Test for Fractal Dimensions.

The U test is useful in the same situations as the independent samples Student's t -test, and the question arises of which should be preferred.

Ordinal data. Choosing the U remains the most logical action when the data are in the form of ordinal measurement and not interval scaled,

for the purpose that the spacing between adjacent values will not be assumed as constant (Motulsky, 2007).

Robustness. Since Mann-Whitney compares the sums of ranks, it is less likely to falsely indicate significance than the t -test because of the presence of outliers. It means that Mann-Whitney is better than t -test in terms of robustness as a statics test. This holds as well for the proposed test for the equality of fractal dimensions i.e. the test for equality of fractal dimensions based on the MLE of θ is less affected by outliers (Motulsky, 2007).

Efficiency. MWW has an (asymptotic) efficiency of or about 0.95 when compared to the t test if the data distribution adheres to normality. For distributions that do not follow normality and for those with large sized, the MWW can better than t in terms of efficiency (Mann, & Whitney, 1947)

When non-normality holds and the distributions are actually fractals, the MWW has an asymptotic efficiency of $\frac{1}{12(1-\lambda)^2}$ relative to the test based on fractal dimensions (FDT). Note that MWW can be more efficient than the test based on fractal dimensions for low dimensional fractals but can also be quite inefficient for high dimensional fractals. In this case also, the asymptotic efficiency of the test based on fractal dimensions (FDT) is 100% relative to the t -test (note that the mean and variance do not exist in the case of fractal distributions).

In the event that the distributions involved are actually fractal distributions, MWW and FDT are competing tests and it may, in fact, be more reasonable to use the FDT for higher fractal dimensions than the Mann-Whitney test.

Kruskal-Wallis-Like Test for Fractal Distributions

The Kruskal-Wallis test assumes that the shapes of the distributions are identical and are scaled for each group, unless there are any differences in the medians (Gargantini & Fraser, 2011). In the case of random variables distributed according to a fractal distribution, the scales are different (but the random pattern persists for each scale). For this reason, we perform the log-transformation:

$Y_{ij} = \log(X_{ij}/\theta)$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, n_p$, $j = 1, 2, \dots, g$ prior to undertaking a Kruskal-Wallis test.

Originality Index:	96 %
Similarity Index:	4 %
Paper ID:	664740066
Grammarly:	Checked

Selvam, A. M. (2009). Fractal fluctuations and statistical normal distribution. *Fractals*, 17(03), 333-349.

References

- Devaney, R. L. (1988). Fractal patterns arising in chaotic dynamical systems. In H. O. Peitgen & D Saupe (Eds.). *The science of fractal images* (pp. 137-168). New York, USA: New York.
- Fay, M. P., & Proschan, M. A. (2010). Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney or t-test? On assumptions for hypothesis tests and multiple interpretations of decision rules. *Statistics Surveys*, 4, 1-39.
- Gargantini, A., & Fraser, G. (2011). Generating minimal fault detecting test suites for general Boolean specifications. *Information and Software Technology*, 53(11), 1263-1273.
- Huber, P. J. (2011). Robust statistics. In M. Lovric (Ed.) *International encyclopedia of statistical science* (pp. 1248-1251). Switzerland: Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
- Mandelbrot, B. B. (1967). How long is the coast of Britain. *Science*, 156(3775), 636-638.
- Mann, H. B., & Whitney, D. R. (1947). On a test of whether one of two random variables is stochastically larger than the other. *The annals of mathematical statistics*, 8(1), 50-60.
- McKnight, P. E., & Najab, J. (2010). Mann-Whitney U Test. *Corsini Encyclopedia of Psychology*. New Jersey, USA: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- Motulsky, H. J. (2007). Prism 5 statistics guide, 2007. *GraphPad Software*, 31(1), 39-42.
- Nachar, N. (2008). The Mann-Whitney U: A test for assessing whether two independent samples come from the same distribution. *Tutorials in Quantitative Methods for Psychology*, 4(1), 13-20.
- Padua, R. N., Barabat, E. O., Borres, M. S., & Salazar, R. K. (2013). Some Results on Multifractal Spectral Analysis. *Recoletos Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 1(2), 57-63.